

Impact of Refined Bi-dimensional Reflector Models on Steel and Water Reflected PWRs

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ABSTRACT

For the usual two-step calculation scheme, many methods of generating reflector parameters have been developed in the past. The usual practice in industrial calculations for such methods makes use of the Generalized Equivalence Theory in order to obtain reflector parameters from a one-dimensional non-fundamental mode transport calculation. The legacy Baff-Refl procedure is an example of such method. In this paper, BREBI, a 2D refined extension of the Baff-Refl reflector procedure has been implemented and tested for small PWRs with the two most encountered types of PWR reflectors in industry : a steel reflector and a water reflector. The aim of this study is to determine the impact and sensitivity of such refinement on usual PWR reflectors in terms of power distribution. The results show that refining the output mesh and generalizing the method to 2D leads to sensible changes in power distribution for 2 groups diffusion calculations with 2x2 nodes per assembly. The power distributions were compared to a 2D MOC transport calculation and the comparisons have shown that the power discrepancy improves for steel-reflected PWRs whereas they worsen for usual water-reflected PWRs. These results, combined with environment and equivalence bias considerations, lead to the conclusion that error cancellations are at play for water reflected PWRs. Finally, the study propose ways of improving the calculation scheme by individually addressing the cancelling sources of bias while keeping the simplicity of the calculation scheme.

Keywords: Diffusion theory, Neutron reflectors, Generalized Equivalence Theory, Discontinuity Factors

1. INTRODUCTION

For means of industrial design, safety and operation, reactor calculation schemes have been developed in order to simulate the state of a full reactor while achieving cost efficiency, accuracy and simplicity.

The two-step calculation scheme achieves these three criteria and is therefore still widely prevalent. The first step is the Lattice calculation which accurately solves the transport equation for a part of the reactor, mostly by solving an infinite-lattice transport problem for each assembly in a wide range of physical states. The results of the Lattice calculations are then homogenized and tabulated in multi-parametrized libraries. These libraries are then interpolated in the second step, the Core calculation that solves a simplified version of the transport equation with a simplified transport operator, homogenized parts of the reactor and a coarse energy description. [1]

In order to preserve the reaction rates between the Lattice calculation and the Core calculation, the scheme has to go through the process of flux-volume averaging and through an equivalence calculation

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because the transport operator in the Core calculation is simplified. [2]

The means of obtaining reflector homogenized parameters for the neutron reflector are not as straightforward as they are for assembly calculation. This is mostly due to the fact that the reflector behavior cannot be modeled in infinite-lattice geometry. Indeed, the fuel-reflector interaction has to be modeled with an active fuel environment and is thus dependent on the choice of the environment. [3]

These constraints have led to different methods of calculating reflector parameters. Some try to model the so-called reflector response with response preservation methods (ERM, Lefebvre-Lebigot, Koebeke, Bêta) [4, 5, 6], some preserve the reaction rates of a chosen lattice geometry (SPH and GET based methods such as Baff-Refl and BREBI) [3] while some try to do both (LERM) [7]. These methods have been developed and validated in the context of PWR designs with reflectors made mainly of water. Now that designs with heavy reflectors have emerged, new investigations on these methods are of practical interest.

The legacy Baff-Refl procedure uses the GET to preserve the reaction rates of a chosen 1D Lattice calculation. The reflector parameters given out by this procedure are the homogenized cross sections and diffusion coefficient from the single macro-geometry node, and the discontinuity factors at the fuel-reflector interface. These parameters are used for every reflector node in the subsequent nodal calculation. [3]

This paper presents the study of the impact of two theoretical improvements to the legacy Baff-Refl : generalization to 2D reflector calculation and refinement of the output mesh.

2. TWO-DIMENSIONAL NODAL EQUIVALENCE : THE BREBI REFLECTOR METHOD

The BREBI (Baff-Refl BIdimensional) procedure is an extension of the Baff-Refl procedure that allows 2D geometries and mesh refinement for nodal diffusion core calculations.

2.1. The BREBI principle

Figure 1. The BREBI sweeping procedure

The goal of BREBI is to introduce azimuthal dependence of reflector parameters for the core calculation.

The principle of the GET is to provide an extra degree of freedom for the two-node problem in order to preserve reference net currents. This principle works in conjunction with the fact that the nodal update procedure in traditional nodal diffusion solvers consists of regularly performing separate two-node problems for each interface of the problem. [2]

For this reason, generalizing the DF generation to 2D requires the BREBI procedure to have a sweeping procedure. This sweeping procedure performs a successive set of 1 node problem with net-current imposed for the x axis at the node boundaries, taking into account transverse leakage in y. Then, the same procedure is carried out in the y direction accounting for transverse leakage in x as depicted in Figure 1.

The entire BREBI procedure is similar to the Baff-Refl procedure [3] and the LERM procedure [7] and consists in performing the following steps :

1. Perform a S_n calculation for a 2D fuel-reflector geometry with
 - P_n scattering anisotropy, $n \geq 1$
 - A fixed geometric buckling is imposed to the Boltzmann equation in order to represent transverse leakage: $B^2 = \left(\frac{\pi}{L_z}\right)^2$ with L_z being the height of the core.
 - Use a fine-group ($G \geq 99$ groups) leakage spectra $L_{i,j,g} = d_{i,j,g} B^2 \phi_{i,j,g}$ where the fine-group leakage coefficients are obtained from the Inscatter model.
2. Homogenize and condense leakage coefficients $d_{i,j,g}$ and cross sections to two-group and few-region geometry (here either 1 node per assembly or 2x2 nodes per assembly)
3. Recover condensed interface fluxes $\phi_{i,j,g}^{\pm*}$ and interface net currents $J_{i,j,g}^{\pm*}$ for each node of the macro-geometry. In some codes such as DRAGON5, interface fluxes and currents can not be recovered directly. The interface fluxes and currents have to be replaced with averaged fluxes and currents over a small interface-like volume gap. In order to preserve the neutron balance, the currents have to undergo a normalization procedure. This procedure is a pseudo-inverse system that solves for small normalization factors that preserve the neutron balance of each node while keeping the directional information of the reference currents.
4. Perform the sweeping procedure solving 1 node problems with $J_{i,j,g}^{\pm*}$ obtained from the S_n reference calculation. The corresponding equations are provided in the literature. The transverse leakage approximation must be the same one as in the subsequent nodal calculation. [8]
 - Compute the interface nodal fluxes $\phi_{i,j,g}^{\pm}$ using the flux expansion
 - For interfaces inside the domain, compute the corresponding interface discontinuity factors with $f_{i,j,g}^{\pm} = \frac{\phi_{i,j,g}^{\pm*}}{\phi_{i,j,g}^{\pm}}$
 - For interfaces at the boundaries of the domain, compute the corresponding albedos with $\Lambda_g^{\pm} = \frac{J_{i,j,g}^{\pm*}}{\phi_{i,j,g}^{\pm}}$

Note that in the 2D case, for the equivalence to be exact, the leakage profile in this step has to be the same one as the one in the core calculation.

5. Normalize the Discontinuity Factors in order to preserve the DF ratio at the fuel-reflector interface.

2.2. Methodology

To study the impacts of BREBI compared to Baff-Refl, namely azimuthal dependence and mesh refinement, a benchmark of 4 different small cores is chosen, with either a homogeneous or a heterogeneous loading pattern and either a homogeneous water reflector or a steel reflector as depicted in Figure 2a. For readability purposes, only the results for the heterogeneous core are shown.

The investigation of two different types of reflectors allows more insight into the benefit of such improved procedure with regards to usual ones.

(a) Studied core with studied reflector zone in red (b) Reflector geometries studied : DFs used in red

Figure 2. Different loading patterns for the study

This study compares the average nodal power between 2 groups and 2x2 nodes per assembly nodal calculations with BRISINGR, a NEM solver developed at Framatome [8], against a 99g MOC full-core calculation with APOLLO3®[9]. The 99g mesh is chosen to facilitate comparison to legacy results and to ease eventual calculation on larger cores.

For fuel assemblies, the parameters from usual infinite medium calculations are used. For the reflector, the BREBI parameters are used. In order to control for self-shielding and energy-mesh biases, the assembly infinite medium calculation and the reference calculation are carried out with the same self-shielding options and energy mesh.

The fact that the reflector is already homogeneous in the studied geometry allows the investigation of the equivalence effects separately from the environment effects and its dependence on the flux spectrum in the flux-volume averaging process.

With the same reasoning, the fuel assemblies used in the lattice transport reflector calculation are homogeneous and with 99g in order to stay coherent with the legacy Baff-Refl procedure that uses a 1D transport step with a homogeneous fuel. The lattice transport reflector geometry is an entire core but for readability purposes the studied zone (shown in Figure 2a) is only a part of the core worthy of investigations (depicted in the red frame of the figure).

The variations studied are added successively starting from the legacy 1D Baff-Refl procedure in order to investigate each contribution independently, as depicted in Figure 2b with geometry A, B, C and D.

2.3. Results

2.3.1. Variation of Discontinuity Factors

The output of the BREBI procedure allows us to gauge the magnitude of the equivalence effects carried by the azimuthal dependence and by the mesh refinement.

1.0001	0.9998	0.9998	1.0001	0.9908	0.9944						
1.0	0.9992	0.9989	0.9984	0.9923	0.9934						
1.0002	0.9998	1.0001	1.0	0.9993	1.002	0.9885	1.0308	0.9363	1.1058	0.9653	0.8177
1.0	1.0	0.9997	1.0006	0.9978	1.004	0.9675	1.0228	0.9919	1.266	0.9913	0.6854
1.0	1.0001	1.0007	1.0014	1.0022	1.0015	1.0015	1.0034	1.0155	1.0122	1.0098	
1.0001	0.9997	0.9977	0.9914	0.9914	0.9768	0.9881	0.9666	0.9741	0.961	0.9875	
0.9999	1.0005	0.9976	1.0048	0.997	1.0025	0.991	1.0254	0.9369	1.1064	0.9689	0.8012
0.9993	1.0013	0.9913	1.0107	0.9887	1.02	0.9697	1.0157	1.0019	1.154	0.9175	-1.1407
1.0001	1.0005	1.0045	1.0102	1.0193	0.9901	1.0283	1.0089	1.05	1.0588	1.0218	
0.9996	0.9985	0.9966	0.9888	0.9561	1.0051	0.9344	0.9973	0.9532	0.9316	0.9751	
0.9996	1.0014	0.9916	1.02	0.9537	1.0598	0.9665	1.0559	0.9561	1.0738	0.9902	0.6852
0.9985	1.0025	0.9769	0.9936	1.0054	1.049	0.9638	1.0624	0.9313	1.2928	1.2066	0.1385
1.0014	1.0025	1.0032	1.018	1.0518	1.0436	1.0883	1.1416	1.9666	1.2276	1.0361	
0.9916	0.9769	0.9891	0.9673	0.9682	0.962	0.9683	0.9731	0.9884	1.1503	0.9885	
0.9966	1.0032	0.9891	1.0273	0.9355	1.0929	0.9663	1.0243	0.9524	1.1366	1.0509	0.4801
0.9888	1.018	0.9673	1.0124	0.9997	1.1401	0.974	1.0258	0.9401	1.1631	1.0913	0.3005
1.02	0.9936	1.0273	1.0124	1.0525	1.0606	1.0222	1.0228	0.7048	0.2551	0.7691	
0.9537	1.0054	0.9355	0.9997	0.9551	0.9319	0.9552	0.9422	0	0	0	
0.9561	1.0518	0.9682	1.0525	0.9551	1.0674	0.9865	0.7116	0	0	0	
1.0051	1.0436	0.962	1.0606	0.9319	1.2461	1.163	0.2289	0	0	0	
1.0598	1.049	1.0929	1.1401	1.0674	1.2461	1.1355		0	0	0	
0.9665	0.9638	0.9663	0.974	0.9865	1.163	1.0391	1.0778	0	0	0	
0.9344	1.0883	0.9683	1.0222	0.9552	1.1107	1.0391	0.5297	0	0	0	
0.9973	1.1416	0.9731	1.0268	0.9422	1.1355	1.0778	0.3407	0	0	0	
1.0558	1.0624	1.0243	1.0258	0.7116	0.2289	0.5287	0.3407	0	0	0	

Figure 3. Output of BREBI : 2-groups Discontinuity Factors map (reflector in red)

The Figure 3 illustrates the 2D dependence of discontinuity factors on a refined 2x2 node per assembly output mesh for the steel reflector of the benchmark.

Compared to the legacy Baff-Refl procedure, three non-trivial phenomena can be observed in BREBI :

- The blue frame shows the typical azimuthal dependence of Discontinuity Factors for a 2D geometry close to the edge of the core. The biggest and most significant variation is a 2% increase of the f_1 in the inner reflector edge. The same order of magnitude is observed for the water reflector.
- The green frame illustrates the fact that, even if there is homogeneous sections on the lattice calculation, the equivalence still outputs non-trivial discontinuity factors that correct for transport effects and spectrum recondensation when approaching the core periphery.
- The red frame shows that for a 2x2 refined mesh in the reflector, non-trivial intra-reflector Discontinuity Factors can carry transport information to the core calculation.

2.3.2. Steel Reflector

The power discrepancy from the study of Figure 2 for the full Heavy reflected core is provided in Figure 4.

Figure 4. Impact of mesh refining and 2D discontinuity factors on the full steel reflected core

These results show that the introduction of 2D dependent and intra-reflector discontinuity factors improve the accuracy of the calculation. The incremental step methodology is used to differentiate between 2D dependence and intra-reflector effects. It is observed that intra-reflector DFs account for the greater part of the improvement.

The way the power shape moves with the added intra-reflector DFs can be explained by the added physical transport information inside the reflector. This grants more out-going transport effects to the 2x2 reflector compared to the coarse mesh 1x1 reflectors which are more diffusive. More neutrons are therefore going out of the reflector thus correcting the bias in the legacy mesh.

2.3.3. Water Reflector

Figure 5. Impact of mesh refining and 2D discontinuity factors on the full water reflected core

The same conclusion can be reached in terms of sensitivity for impacts in water reflected cores. However, in contrast to the steel reflected core, these effects seem to degrade the power accuracy. The physical mechanism in play with the added 2D intra-reflector DFs indicates that an error compensation may have been decompensated, possibly revealing the true extent of the environment bias of peripheral assemblies for water-reflected cores.

3. CONCLUSIONS

Investigations on the impact of 2D discontinuity factors for reflectors and intra-reflector DFs have shown that there is a non-negligible impact on core power distribution. For both types of reflectors, the core power distribution is more sensitive to the use of intra-reflector DFs and moderately sensitive to the use of 2D discontinuity factors.

Compared to a full-core transport calculation, both effects impact the steel-reflected core power distribution positively. However, for the water-reflected core these effects negatively impact the power distribution.

A plausible explanation for this phenomenon is that an error cancellation is into play between the environment effects from peripheral assemblies and the equivalence effects of the legacy reflector scheme without intra-reflector DFs.

The peripheral assemblies underestimate the reactivity in the infinite medium approximation for the water reflector since it doesn't take into account the near reflector moderation in its cross-sections. On the other side, using intra-reflector DFs introduces more transport-like behaviour through its corrections which leaks more neutrons and underestimates the reactivity of the peripheral assemblies. Not using intra-reflector DFs therefore overestimates this reactivity and cancels out the environment effect of the peripheral assemblies.

For the heavy reflector, the peripheral environment effect is less important but the equivalence effect is still present which explains the overestimation of the peripheral assemblies reactivity. This also explains why there is improvement when the intra-reflector discontinuity factors are introduced.

Further efforts are to be made to correct the environment effects of peripheral assemblies. In parallel, the use of DF-like matrices has proven to work inside traditional nodal codes. Using the matrix properties to address these environmental effects seems promising. Since the BREBI procedure and the LERM procedure [7] are not mutually exclusive, both principles could be combined in order to model a wide range of environment effects inside the core.

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